

Chelate Formation between Iron (III) and Sulphodichloro-hydroxydimethyl Fuchson Dicarboxylic Acid (Trisodium Salt): Studies on the Composition and Stability

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A detailed study has been made on the composition and stability of the chelate formed between iron (III) and sulphodichlorohydroxydimethyl fuchson dicarboxylic acid (Chrome Azurol S), using absorbance and electrical conductance measurements. The chelate has a composition 1:1, maximum absorption at 570 m μ , and it is stable between pH 2.5 and 4.5. The values of log K as determined by the continued variation method and the mole-ratio method, using absorbance data, are 4.8 ± 0.1 and 4.9 ± 0.1 respectively at 25°, pH 3.0, and ionic strength 0.1M. The free-energy change of formation, calculated from the two values of log K , comes to -6.58 ± 0.14 and -6.72 ± 0.14 K cal. respectively.

Dyes of the hydroxytriphenylmethane group are well known for their tendency of forming coloured chelates with various metal ions. An important member of this group of dyes is sulphodichlorohydroxydimethyl fuchson dicarboxylic acid (trisodium salt), which is commonly known as Chrome Azurol S (abbreviated as CAS), and is represented by the following structure:

They¹ observed qualitatively that Chrome Azurol S formed coloured lakes with beryllium (II), copper (II), iron (III), aluminium (III), zirconium (IV), and lead (II), but details were not reported. A detailed study of the colour reactions of the metal ions with this reagent made by us² shows that it forms very stable coloured chelates in ammoniacal solutions with Mg (II), Ni (II), Co (II), Zn (II), and Cd (II). Coloured lakes are also formed with Ti (IV), Ce (IV), La (III), Th (IV), and many rare earths in neutral or slightly acidic media.

Srivastava and Dey³ have made a detailed study of the metal chelates of Chrome Azurol S with Cu (II), Be (II), Al (III), Th (IV), and U (VI). Seth and Dey⁴ have deter-

1. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1955, 144, 106.

2. Dey *et al.*, Proc. 7th Int. Conf. Co-ord. Chem., Stockholm & Uppsala, 1962, pp. 330-332.

3. Srivastava, Doctoral thesis, Allahabad Univ., 1960; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, in press.

4. Seth, Doctoral thesis, Allahabad Univ., 1961.

mined the composition and stability of the metal chelates of Mg(II) and Zr(IV) with CAS.

This communication describes the studies on the composition and stability of the iron(III)-CAS chelate. The composition has been determined by various methods including absorbance measurements and corroborated further by electrical conductance studies.

EXPERIMENTAL

B. D. H. AnalaR sample of ferric chloride was used for making the solutions. Chrome Azurole S solution (B.D.H. indicator) was the same as used previously⁵. Other chemicals employed were of the reagent grade.

Absorbance, conductance, and H-ion concentration measurements were carried out as reported in earlier communications⁵.

All experiments were performed in an air-conditioned room maintained at $25^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$. The total volume of all the mixtures prepared for the measurements was kept at 50 ml. The individual solutions and mixtures were kept immersed in a Townson and Mercer's precision thermostat maintaining a temperature of $25^{\circ} \pm 0.01^{\circ}$ for about an hour, which was sufficient for their equilibration and for attaining the temperature of the bath.

pH of the solutions and mixtures was adjusted to 3.0 ± 0.2 by addition of suitable amounts of hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide. Ionic strength was also kept constant at 0.1M by addition of sodium perchlorate.

Procedure.—The composition of the chelate was studied by (i) Job's method⁶ (using absorbance as well as electrical conductance measurements), (ii) Yoe and Jones' mole-ratio method⁷, and (iii) Harvey and Manning's slope-ratio method⁸ [(ii) and (iii) using absorbance measurements only].

Evaluation of the Stability Constant

Among the procedures adopted for the determination of stability of coloured complexes, a convenient method is that described by Anderson and co-workers⁹ which is based on the comparison of the composition of mixtures having identity of colour, i.e., the same absorbance values. The method, however, suffers from a limitation that both the interacting solutions forming the complex must be colorless. Dey *et al.*¹⁰ modified the method to calculate the stability of complexes in solution, where one of the reactants may be coloured. This method has been employed here to calculate the stability constant and the value has been compared with that obtained by the mole-ratio method.

5. Sinha and Dey, *this Journal*, 1962, **39**, 469; Seth and Dey, *ibid.*, p. 724.

6. *Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **x**, 9, 113; 1936, **xi**, 6, 07.

7. *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4448.

9. *Ibid.*, 1948, **70**, 1195; 1949, **71**, 909, 912.

10. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **6**, 314; *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, **18**, 324; Proc. Symp. Chem. Co-ord. Compds., Agra, 1960, **2**, 198.

DISCUSSION

Behaviour of the Reagent as a Colloidal Electrolyte.—The reagent behaves as a colloidal electrolyte, as reported earlier¹¹, and hence dilute solutions of Chrome Azurol S of the order of $10^{-4}M$ and $10^{-5}M$ were employed during these studies.

Effect of Time on the Colour of the Chelate.—Colour formation was observed to be instantaneous and it was found that even up to 48 hours, there was no change in the absorbance values.

FIG. 1. Absorption spectra studies of mixtures of ferric chloride and CAS.
[pH 3.0 ± 0.2 ; $\mu 0.1$ (NaClO_4)].

Curve A	: Reagent	$6.67 \times 10^{-5}M$.
Curve B	: c =	13.34×10^{-5} ; p = 0.5.
Curve C	: c =	6.67×10^{-5} ; p = 1.0.
Curve D	: c =	3.33×10^{-5} ; p = 2.0.
Curve E	: c =	2.22×10^{-5} ; p = 3.0.
Curve F	: c =	1.67×10^{-5} ; p = 4.0.

Nature of the Complexes Formed.—The method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹² was employed to determine the nature of the complexes formed in solution. Mixtures containing 2:1, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 ratios of iron to CAS were prepared, keeping the total volume 50 ml in each case. Absorbance measurements were carried out between a range of 350 m μ and 750 m μ at 5 m μ or 10 m μ intervals, as required. The observations have graphically been plotted in Fig. 1. It is evident from the curve A that the region of maximum absor-

11. Srivastava *et al.*, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1962, 17, 86.

12. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1630.

bance of the reagent lies at 480 m μ . In curves B,C,D,E, and F the wave length of maximum absorbance shifts to 570 m μ . This shows clearly that only one complex is formed in solution under the conditions of study.

Stoichiometry of the Components.—The composition was established by the aforementioned methods. A large number of observations were taken. Some of the typical results are plotted in Figs. 2 to 7.

FIG. 2. Determination of the composition from absorption spectra studies of equimolecular solutions at 570 m μ ; $p=1$, $pH=3.0\pm 0.2$, μ 0.1 (NaClO_4).

Curve A: $c = 1.66 \times 10^{-4} M$
 Curve B: $c = 1.25 \times 10^{-4}$
 Curve C: $c = 1.00 \times 10^{-4}$
 Curve D: $c = 0.83 \times 10^{-4}$

FIG. 3. Determination of the composition from absorption spectra studies of non-equimolecular solutions at 570 m μ ; pH 3.0 ± 0.2 , μ 0.1 (NaClO_4).

Curve A: $c = 1.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 1.66$.
 Curve B: $c = 2.00 \times 10^{-4}$; $p = 0.83$.

Table I summarises the results on the composition of the chelate arrived at from the examination of Figs. 2 and 3, when the method of continued variation was employed using absorbance measurements. In the legends, c represents the concentration of ferric chloride and p , the ratio c'/c (c' being the concentration of the chelating agent).

The results of the method of continued variation using electrical conductance measurements (Figs. 4-5) are summarised in Table II.

FIG. 4. Determination of the composition from electrical conductance studies of equimolecular solutions).

Curve A: $c = 8.33 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 1.00$.
 Curve B: $c = 2.50 \times 10^{-4}$; $p = 1.00$.
 Curve C: $c = 1.66 \times 10^{-4}$; $p = 1.00$.

FIG. 5. Determination of the composition from electrical conductance studies of non-equimolecular solutions.

Curve A: $c = 1.66 \times 10^{-4} M$; $p = 2.00$.
 Curve B: $c = 1.66 \times 10^{-4}$; $p = 1.50$.

TABLE I

Fig. No.	Curve.	$c \times 10^4$.	p .	λ .	Vol. of $FeCl_3$ at the peak	Comp. of the chelate, $Fe(III) : CAS$.
2	A	1.66M	1.00	570 m μ	20.0 ml	1:1
	B	1.23	1.00	570	20.0	1:1
	C	1.00	1.00	570	20.0	1:1
	D	0.83	1.00	570	20.0	1:1
*2(a)	A	1.66	1.00	580	20.0	1:1
	B	1.25	1.00	580	20.0	1:1
	C	1.00	1.00	580	20.0	1:1
	D	0.83	1.00	580	20.0	1:1
3	A	1.00	1.66	570	25.0	1:1
	B	2.00	0.83	570	15.0	1:1
*3(a)	A	1.00	1.66	580	25.0	1:1
	B	2.00	0.83	580	15.0	1:1

*Omitted to economise space.

TABLE II

Fig. No.	Curve.	$c \times 10^4$.	p .	Vol. of FeCl_3 at the peak	Comp. of the chelate, Fe(III):CAS .
4	A	3.33M	1.00	25.0 ml	1:1
	B	2.50	1.00	25.0	1:1
	C	1.66	1.00	25.0	1:1
5	A	1.66	2.00	15.0	1:1
	B	1.66	1.50	20.0	1:1

From the tables, the ratio of iron to CAS in the chelate appears to be 1:1 and it may be represented as Fe(CAS) . The same composition of the chelate is also arrived at by the mole-ratio method (Fig. 6) and the slope-ratio method (Fig. 7).

FIG. 6. Determination of the composition from absorbance studies by the mole-ratio method at $570\text{m}\mu$.

Curves A and B refer respectively to CAS conc. of $6.67 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; $\text{pH} = 3.0 \pm 0.2$, $0.1 (\text{NaClO}_4)$.

Influence of H-ion Concentration on the Stability of the Chelate.—The absorbance of mixtures containing ferric chloride and CAS in the ratio 1:1 (each $3.00 \times 10^{-5} M$) at different pH's were measured at various wave lengths. λ_{max} of the chelate is $570\text{m}\mu$ between pH 2.5 and 5.5, indicating that the chelate is stable within this range of pH. The variation with pH in colour intensity of the chelate at its λ_{max} is also represented in Fig. 8.

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FIG. 7. Determination of the composition from absorbance studies by the slope-ratio method at 570 mμ (●) and 580 mμ (Δ). pH=3.0±0.2. 20 ml excess component $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M + x$ ml variable component $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M + (30 - x)$ ml H₂O.

FIG. 8. Variation in colour intensity with change in pH at 570 mμ. $c = 3.00 \times 10^{-5} M$; $p = 1.00$.

Calculation of the Stability Constant.—The values of $\log K$ (at fixed pH and ionic strength), as determined by two different methods (Figs. 6 and 9), are shown in Table III. The free-energy change of formation has also been calculated with the help of the expression:

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K,$$

the terms having their usual meaning.

FIG. 9. Determination of the stability constant from absorbance data at 570 $m\mu$. Concentrations, pH , and μ , same as in Fig. 2.

TABLE III

Method.	pH .	Ionic strength.	$\log K$.	ΔG° at 25° (Kcals.).
Dey <i>et al.</i>	3.0 ± 0.2	0.1M (NaClO_4)	4.8 ± 0.1	-6.58 ± 0.14
Mole ratio	3.0 ± 0.2	0.1M (NaClO_4)	4.9 ± 0.1	-6.72 ± 0.14

It is clear from the above table that the results obtained by both the methods are in close conformity with each other and establish the reliability of the values.

Suggestions on the Structure of the Chelate.—Colour of CAS has been found to change with variation in H^+ -ion concentration of the medium. The wave length of maximum absorbance of the reagent depends on the pH (Table IV).

TABLE IV

pH .	λ_{max} .
1.5—5.2	485, 490 $m\mu$
6.0—10.2	425
11.7 and above	595

Hence, the following structures appear to be reasonable for the reagent in the acidic, neutral, and alkaline media:

(i) Acidic medium.

(ii) Neutral medium.

(iii) Alkaline medium.

From the experimental results reported in this paper, it is not possible to obtain definite information on the position of the chelate ring, but some tentative structure of the chelate might be suggested. There are two alternative positions where chelation might occur. The metal ion may be co-ordinated either between the quinoid oxygen and the adjacent carboxylic oxygen or between the phenolic oxygen and the adjacent

carboxylic oxygen. It may be noted that the wave length of maximum absorbance is found to be 570 m μ .

In a strongly alkaline medium, where the structure suggests removal of the phenolic hydrogen by ionisation, the λ_{max} of the reagent alone lies at 595 m μ . On the other hand, in a mildly alkaline medium or an acidic medium, the wave length of maximum absorbance is found to be at 425 m μ and near about 465 m μ . Thus it is suggested that as a result of chelation, the phenolic hydrogen is replaced and hence the wave length of maximum absorbance of the chelate is more near the structure (iii) rather than structures (i) and (ii). It may therefore be reasonably assumed that chelation in this case occurs between the phenolic and carboxylic oxygens and not between the quinoid and the adjacent carboxylic oxygens. This would lead to the formation of anionic complex, which has further been confirmed by the complete adsorption of the colour of the chelate by ion exchange resin Amberlite, IR-45(OH) (B.D.H. AnalaR).

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